

IMPORTANCE OF USING GAMES IN EFL CLASSROOMS

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Abstract. *The purpose of this paper is to investigate how games are useful and effective in EFL courses. In this study, two types of qualitative research methodologies were used: semi-structured interviews and observation. Based on the results, it was established that games should be used in second language learning classrooms to provide an environment for EFL learners that is entertaining, motivating, and conducive to excellent learning performance.*

Key words: *EFL classrooms, games, vocabulary.*

ВАЖНОСТЬ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ ИГР В КЛАССАХ EFL

Аннотация. *Цель этой статьи - исследовать, насколько игры полезны и эффективны на курсах EFL. В этом исследовании были использованы два типа методик качественного исследования: полуструктурированные интервью и наблюдение. Основываясь на результатах, было установлено, что игры следует использовать в классах для изучения второго языка, чтобы создать для учащихся EFL среду, которая была бы развлекательной, мотивирующей и способствовала отличной успеваемости.*

Ключевые слова: *классы EFL, игры, словарный запас.*

1. Introduction

One of the most significant components in EFL lessons is games. They include activities that have goals and restrictions while also being enjoyable. According to Hadfield (1990; cited in Deesri, 2002, p.1), games are "an activity with rules, a goal, and an element of fun." Language games, according to some writers, should be placed at the heart of the foreign language instruction program rather than being recognized as a peripheral aspect of the program since, in addition to being fun, they involve goals and are governed by rules (Haldfield, 1999).

According to S. M. Silvers, author of Games for the Classroom and English Speaking Club, games are frequently agreed upon by many teachers as instruments that interrupt repetitive repetitions in the lesson and are used to fill in time (Silvers 1992). He says that many teachers frequently overlook the fact that actual learning can occur in a relaxed environment, and that learners are able to utilize the target language that they have been exposed to and used previously. According to Greenall's definition, games foster good competitiveness among students participating in a linguistic activity (Greenall, 1990).

The fact that learners provide a lot of benefits through games demonstrates support for using games in a foreign language classroom. Many knowledgeable writers confirmed that games are educationally useful. Lee mentions some of the following causes (Lee, 1995): Games provide an opportunity to escape from an odd routine, but they are also crucial in terms of motivation and challenges. Furthermore, games give learners with motivation to interact and communicate successfully, as well as the persistence to continue the effort of learning and establish a context to

use the language meaningfully, which reduces anxiety and allows learners to study in a pleasant and fun environment.

Another advantage of employing games in a foreign language setting is that it helps to clarify tense situations. A stress-free environment should be offered in a language-learning environment. At this moment, games are particularly beneficial because learners do not feel anxious, and their positive attitudes and self-confidence improve because they are not frightened of being punished or scolded while freely learning the language (Crookal, 1990).

The purpose of this paper is to demonstrate the importance of games in EFL courses. The role of games in EFL courses will be examined in length in the following section.

2. Literature Review

One of the most crucial elements of EFL classrooms are games. They contain enjoyable activities with objectives and rules. Games, according to Hadfield (1990; cited in Deesri, 2002), are "an activity with rules, a goal, and an element of fun." Games that teach foreign languages can be used as a framework to provide language learning a purposeful setting. According to Constantinescu (2012), playing games can help students get a better knowledge of both spoken and written English. Games aid in the context-based learning of words and grammatical structures using proper pronunciation and spelling.

Despite the fact that the majority of teachers are unaware of games as a learning approach, they play a significant role in language learning classes. However, it provides a number of advantages for learners' learning processes. First off, games save the lecture from being routine and uninteresting. On the other hand, they foster a productive and encouraging learning environment where the emphasis is on the students and their education. Games always make learning enjoyable for students, which is why they are more engaging than regular sessions. The games in the classroom assist the students learn the language while having fun. Even reserved and reticent kids respond favorably to them (Mei & Yu-Jing, 2000). Children are more motivated as a result because they play as a substitute activity, which motivates pupils to maintain interest in the lesson and keep working. In doing so, they lessen the pressure associated with learning a new language (Mei & Yu-jing, 2000).

Games have several benefits for encouraging the acquisition of the target language in EFL classrooms. As games are used, students' concern over language acquisition lessens, which is one of the benefits linked with them. In language classes, students make the assumption that they must succeed in the target language, even though they do not. Additionally, students experience a great deal of anxiety as a result of their teacher criticizing and punishing them when they make a mistake. Games now take center stage because they help learners practice the target language without concern for punishment or judgment, which lowers anxiety, boosts positive emotions, and improves self-confidence (Crookal, 1990).

According to Crookall (1990), since students actively participate in the games, they are referred to as learner-centered activities. Through games, roles between students and teachers are altered, and teachers urge students to actively engage in their learning. Games, therefore allow students an opportunity to be in charge of their own education. Another benefit of games from an educational standpoint is that they provide a framework for language use that is relevant. Teachers can create a variety of situations through the use of games that enable students to learn

subconsciously because they are not focused on the message or the language. As a result, when they concentrate on playing a game as an activity, they pick up the target language in the same way they pick up their native tongue—without even realizing it (Cross, 2000).

According to Constantinescu (2012):

- Games help learners increase their English vocabulary in a familiar and comfortable setting (even for children who may have specific needs), where they feel competent;
- They boost motivation and the drive to develop oneself because they provide a sense of challenge and competitiveness, which makes pupils more focused on finishing the task at hand.
- Interdisciplinary strategy. Students also draw on information from other courses.
- Games help pupils improve their observational skills.
- Games have definite goals and regulations.
- Games foster creative problem-solving, critical thinking, and imagination.
- Games provide fresh and engaging methods of instruction and practice that take the place of conventional workbooks.
- Games can be adjusted for players with various degrees of knowledge.
- Educational games are simple to use and comprehend. It doesn't take long for the class to play educational games.
- Online instructional games are widely available and cost nothing.
- Quick feedback for the teacher and the students. The effects are more audible and occasionally apparent, and they are more powerful.
- The working hours are often agreed upon up front and are observed.

Along with all these benefits, it's also crucial to consider the learners' motivation because they are more motivated to learn the language when they are engaged in a game. This argument is made by McCallum (1980, p. ix), who says that "games automatically stimulate student interest, a properly introduced game can be one of the highest motivating techniques." In addition, games "spur motivation" and "students get very absorbed in the competitive aspects of the games; moreover, they try harder at games than in other courses," according to Avedon (1971; cited in Deesri, 2002). Games thereby increase students' interest in classroom activities, which in turn motivates and increases their desire to study. In addition to many benefits, employing games in EFL classes has certain drawbacks. According to Stojkovic and Jerotijevic (2011), games have a number of drawbacks, including the following:

- 1) discipline problems, rowdy students, and other difficulties;
- 2) Deviating from the game's primary goal, potentially as a result of poor rule training, leading to excessive play and a lack of learning;
- 3) If games are monotonous or already well-known, students might not be as engaged;
- 4) Some students, particularly teens, could consider games pointless and juvenile.

Teachers typically like to utilize games as warm-up exercises or, if there is time, at the conclusion of the session. The teachers use the activities to break up the monotony of the textbook, fill in any additional class time, and prepare students for tests. Furthermore, Rixon (1979) adds that if games are appropriate and carefully designed, they can be used at all levels of the lesson (As mentioned in Uberman, 1998).

In conclusion, when games are used in foreign language classes, they offer language teachers a great deal of educational value and a number of benefits. According to a review of studies on language games, games are extremely important in many circumstances for teaching and learning foreign languages.

3. Methodology

Semi-structured interviews and observation were employed as data gathering methods in this qualitative case study. The rationale behind picking a case study is that it enables the researcher to learn more about the participants' life and collect useful data. The case study research method is an empirical investigation that examines a current phenomenon in its real-life context; when the boundaries between phenomenon and context are not readily visible; and in which many sources of evidence are used. This definition is given by Yin (1984, p. 23). Many researchers (Miles and Huberman, 1994; Debrel, 2012; Silverman, 2011) contend that a qualitative study is more flexible in gathering in-depth background data since it can ask open-ended questions or pay close attention to events and occasions on a regular basis.

Semi-structured interviews

Semi-structured interviews are used in the current study due to the fact that interviews ask questions orally and collect accessible data orally (Kuale, 2006). Semi-structured interviews are preferred over structured ones in part because they allow for the collection of more in-depth data due to the fact that they also involve investigations to get additional exploratory data about the questions. The in-depth comprehension of the interviewees' perceptions, attitudes, and feelings is the additional justification for doing semi-structured interviews. Interviews were used because they allowed researchers to gain insight into variables that could not be immediately seen, such as student attitudes, perceptions, and opinions (Mackey & Gass, 2005). In order to learn more about participants' behaviors and activities in relation to the EFL situation under study, non-participant observations were also used (Mackey & Gass, 2005). In this study, students were interviewed in a semi-structured interview to gain their opinions on using games to acquire English vocabulary. An interview form was created by researchers with this objective in mind. Following the conclusion of all game-related activities, interviews were held with four participants who gave their consent and were informed that their names would be kept private and that their remarks would only be used for study.

Observation

Methods of observation are helpful to researchers in a variety of ways. According to Schmuck (1997), they offer means of regulating nonverbal emotional expression, figuring out how participants connect with one another, and monitoring how much time is spent on particular tasks. Additionally, the researchers find that participant observation is useful for verifying the meanings of terms used by interviewees, monitoring situations where informants may not be able or willing to share ideas that would be impolite or sensitive, and monitoring events that participants have reported in interviews so that they are aware of inaccurate and distorted information provided by those informants (Mars).

Findings

When studying a second language, students must come across strange words, which puts them under a lot of stress. They consequently don't feel safe and at ease, which undoubtedly affects

their capacity to learn. In summary, games help people feel less anxious, more at ease, and curious. It is confirmed that they are amicable and at ease. Since students are aware of this, they can interact naturally while playing games without worrying about making mistakes or editing their own statements. When students are not anxious or stressed, they can improve their speaking and fluency. Additionally, as games are played, learners' anxiety levels drop when they play a game. amplify the good and bolster your confidence. Additionally, students have significant levels of anxiety because they worry about being corrected and disciplined by their teacher when they make a mistake. Games enter the scene at this point because they soothe anxiety, boost pleasant emotions, and boost self-esteem. According to Crookal (1990), learners do not worry about being reprimanded or scolded as they freely use the second language. One of the players said, "While I was playing the game, I did not consider whether I made a mistake or not, I only used the language to convey the message." A different player noted, "While I was playing the game, I was not under any stress, since I was enjoying while presenting the words."

The study's interview and observation data made it clear that the games assisted participants in picking up the language without the need for memory. Furthermore, the findings made it clear that games are helpful tools for helping learners retain the words without consulting any textual sources. When asked if it was simple to remember the words while playing the game, one of the participants replied, "Yes, it was quite simple to recall the words".

4. Conclusion

This study's main goal was to examine the value of incorporating games in EFL lessons. As these results demonstrate, playing games produces an enjoyable and satisfying atmosphere in addition to strong incentive for language acquisition. Additionally, the value of games in reducing language anxiety cannot be understated. Games are crucial for teaching English because they give students a chance to practice the language while also having fun and being entertained with it. In conclusion, games are acceptable as practical and effective teaching aids for vocabulary. In order to deliver more engaging, fun, and productive instruction, games can be used in EFL courses (Uberman, 1998).

As a result of the study's findings, it is clear that games are crucial tools in language-learning classrooms for creating a relaxed environment for students. Games are also very helpful for both teachers and students if they serve an educational purpose in addition to being entertaining.

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